

Event metadata

Event title	Future of AI in Life Sciences
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	29/04/2026
Time of event	2pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are rapidly changing the way we work in the life sciences. Recently, Australian BioCommons called upon the community to share how they apply these technologies to molecular data analysis to help map future needs.</p> <p>Join us for this dedicated webinar where we will share a summary of the findings from our national consultation. This session will explore the general survey results, highlighting the national trends, bottlenecks, and digital infrastructure gaps you've helped identify.</p> <p>It will also include a 'first look' at our initial training program, giving you a sneak peek into the workshops and resources we'll be launching later this year to better support the application of AI in life science research.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/future-of-ai-in-life-sciences
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Artificial intelligence, machine learning, life sciences
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists and support staff at all levels of experience from those who have never used AI to those who rely on it every day - who are

	interested in the future of AI and ML in Australian research.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	NA
Speakers	Dr Minh Huynh, AI in Research Training Lead, Australian BioCommons and Sydney Informatics Hub Dr Benjamin Goudey, AI Technical Lead, Australian BioCommons
Training materials	Materials shared in this Zenodo record: Presentation slides: Future of AI in Life Sciences Webinar.pdf Materials shared elsewhere: YouTube recording: https://youtu.be/yPBuHT1zaqI
Related material	None